

11-16 AUGUST 2019

22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

IMPACT PROPERTIES OF HELICOIDAL STRUCTURE OF CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES

Mazhar Peerzada, Bronwyn Fox and N. Hameed

Faculty of Science, Engineering and Technology, Swinburne University of Technology, Melbourne, Australia

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Fibre Reinforced Composites

Aluminium

Steel

Iron

Isotropic Material

Woven preform

Knitted preform

UD preform

Anisotropic Material

Fibre Reinforced Composites

Aluminium

Steel

Iron

Isotropic Material

Quasi-isotropic Material

Woven preform

Knitted preform

UD preform

Anisotropic Material

Methodology

Impact behavior: Force versus Time with respect to Energy level

Figure 1: Typical force and time curve of (a) different impact energy levels on Bouligand structure (b) different preform structures

Damage Analysis by CT X-ray Tomography

Figure 2: Impact Damage of Helicoidal Structure (i) Virgin (ii) top view - damaged at 20J (iii) side-view - damaged at 20J

Conclusion

- The Helicoidal structure composites absorbed the highest energy and made the highest contact duration at 20J impact energy level whereas the shortest contact duration was seen at 10J impact energy.
- While comparing the structures, bias structure absorbed the highest energy with the lowest contact duration. However, the helicoidal structure absorbed lowest energy with highest contact duration.
- The computerized X-ray tomography image analysis showed that bias structure exhibited higher damage (with dent/depression in composite plate) as compared with other structures.